

TYPES AND RELIABILITY OF INFORMATION.

Abduraimova Rayhona

Student of group 105

Termiz State Pedagogical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7407904>

Reliability is something that shows the quality of data, reflects its completeness and accuracy. It has such characteristics as being clear in written and spoken language, the absence of false or distorted information, the possibility of incorrect use of information blocks, including letters, symbols, bits, numbers. The accuracy of the information and its source are evaluated on a direct scale (for example, "mostly reliable", "completely reliable", "relatively reliable", then "not at all reliable" or "status unspecified").

Reliability describes the integrity of information. This is affected not only by the validity of the data, but also by the accuracy of the methods of obtaining it.

But inaccuracy can mean deliberately preparing information as false. There are cases where there is information that can be characterized as unreliable as a result of incorrect data. This happens when the degree of uncertainty of the information is already known to the receiver during their reception. In general, the following situation is observed: the greater the amount of initial data, the higher the reliability of the data.

Thus, reliability is directly related to the accuracy of information, its completeness and objectivity. This feature is very important, especially when using information to make any decision. Unreliable information leads to such decisions that have negative consequences in terms of social decisions, political situation or economic situation.

Thus, if the information does not correspond to the original state, it is false, it contains information about events, processes or events, which in fact never existed or did not exist. , but the information about them differs from what actually happens, is characterized by the fact that it is distorted or incomplete.

It can be called reliable, it is a fact that does not cause doubt, it is real. This includes, if necessary, information that can be verified by legally sound procedures, when various documents or expert opinions are used, witnesses can be called. In addition, if they are necessary, the data can be considered reliable. primary source. However, in this case, the problem of determining the reliability of the information source arises.

Types of information sources

Sources of information can be:

- persons who have information of interest to various mass media according to their authority or position,
- a real environment (for example, a city, a natural object with human habitation),
- printed publications, i.e. textbooks, books, encyclopedias or magazine articles,
- Internet sites, portals, pages on which mass media may also be based.

Undoubtedly, one of the most authoritative and secure sources are documents, but they are considered so only if there is a possibility of legal verification. They are distinguished by completeness of information.

In addition to being reliable and unreliable, sources can also be competent and incompetent.

Information sources authorized by official authorities are presented the most. First, public institutions should provide citizens with the most objective and accurate information. However, even information from the government press service can be falsified, and there is no guarantee that unreliable information will not spread from government sources. Therefore, getting information does not mean trusting it implicitly.

Inspection methods

Since only factual information is reliable, the ability to verify data and determine its reliability is essential. If you master this skill, you can avoid any misinformation pitfalls. For this, first of all, it is necessary to determine the semantic loading of the received information: factor or calculated.

It is very important to control the accuracy of the information. Facts are primarily what a person encounters when he receives new information for himself. They refer to information that has already been checked for reliability. If information is not verified or cannot be verified, then there are no facts. These include numbers, events, names, dates. You can also measure, confirm, touch or list. Often, sociological and research institutes, agencies specializing in statistics, etc. have the opportunity to provide them. The main feature that evaluates the reliability of facts and data is the objectivity of the first. Evaluation is always a reflection of a person's subjective view or emotional attitude and requires certain actions.

Differentiation of information sources and their comparison

In addition, it is very important to distinguish the sources of information. Since it is impossible to independently verify many facts, the reliability of the received information is considered from the point of view of trusting the sources that provided them. How to check the source of information? The main factor that

determines the truth is how it is considered practical or how it plays an auxiliary role in the performance of a certain task. The dominant criterion of any information is its effectiveness, which is also shown by the number of subjects who used the information. The higher it is, the greater the confidence in the obtained data and the higher their reliability. This is the basic principle of data reliability.

References:

1. ГОСТ 7.0-99. Система стандартов по информации, библиотечному и издательскому делу. Информационно-библиотечная деятельность. Библиография. Термины и определения
2. Piccoli, Gabriele; Pigni, Federico. Information systems for managers: with cases, Edition 4.0, Prospect Press, July 2018 — 28 bet. ISBN 978-1-943153-50-3.
3. O'Hara, Margaret; Watson, Richard; Cavan, Bruce (1999). „Managing the three levels of change“. Information Systems Management. 16-jild, № 3. 64-bet. doi:10.1201/1078/43197.16.3.19990601/31317.9. Qaraldi: 25-noyabr 2018-yil.
4. „Information Systems“ (12-noyabr 2020-yil).
5. „information system“. BusinessDictionary.com. 11-avgust 2020-yilda asl nusxadan arxivlandi. Qaraldi: 2-avgust 2022-yil.
6. „Information Systems“. Principia Cybernetica Web.
7. Vladimir Zwass (2016-02-10). "Information system". Britannica.
8. D'Atri A., De Marco M., Casalino N. (2008). "Interdisciplinary Aspects of Information Systems Studies", Physica-Verlag, Springer, Germany, pp. 1-416, ISBN 978-3-7908-2009-6
9. „Information Technology vs Information Systems: What's The Difference?“ (en-US). CityU of Seattle (16-yanvar 2020-yil). Qaraldi: 13-noyabr 2021-yil.
- 10.

